

Modification of Silkfibroin through Graft Copolymerisation using Acrylonitrile Monomer

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Abstract

The kinetics of acrylonitrile grafted co-polymerization of silk initiated by free radicals formed in situ by ceric ammonium sulphate /oxalic acid redox system was investigated in an aqueous sulphuric acid medium in the laboratory temperature. The rate of graft co-polymerization is proportional to first order of monomer concentration $[M]^{1.0}$; ceric ammonium sulphate is found to be fractional order $[Ce(IV)]^{0.8}$. The temperature – dependence of the rate was studied and the activation parameters were computed using Arrhenius plots. A mechanism consistent with the experimental data involving Ce(IV)- oxalic acid complex formation, which generates free radicals is suggested. The chain termination step of the graft co-polymerization reaction was determined.

Introduction

One trend in modern civilization is to effect gradual replacement of natural materials with either all synthetic materials or modified natural materials. In the polymeric age, it is essential to modify the properties of a polymer according to tailor-made specifications designed for target applications. There are several means to modify polymer properties, viz. blending, grafting, and curing. ‘Blending’ is the physical mixtures of structurally different polymers, or copolymers which interact through secondary forces with no bonding^{1, 2} to obtain the requisite properties. ‘Grafting’ is a method wherein monomers are covalently bonded (modified) onto the polymer chain. Actually, there is no time scale for the process of grafting, which can take minutes, hours or even days, whereas curing is usually a very rapid process, occurring in a fraction of a second. In this review, we concentrated on grafting methods. Two major types of grafting may be considered: (i) grafting with a single monomer and (ii) grafting with a mixture of two (or more) monomers. The first type usually occurs in a single step, but the second may occur with either the simultaneous or sequential use of the two monomers. Mosaic grafting has attracted much attention for binary monomer grafting. Two different monomers are grafted side-by-side to obtain the requisite property. This is the origin of bipolar membranes. The application of Silk fibroin(SF) as a

biomaterial began centuries ago, with its use as sutures for wound treatment. Due to their excellent performance, SF-based biomaterials have been found suitable for a variety of applications, including drug delivery, vascular tissue regeneration, skin wound dressing, and bone tissue scaffolds.

Natural silks are excellent clothing materials with outstanding mechanical and aesthetic characteristics. However, silk lacks some important performance properties like anti-photo yellowing, wash and wear, abrasion resistance, crease proofing, etc., which can be improved by graft copolymerization and/or other chemical modification techniques. 3, 4, 5. Epoxides 6, glycol diglycidyl ether 7, aliphatic and aromatic dibasic acid anhydrides 8, 9, 10 have been used for chemical modification of silk and wool¹¹ for improving fiber and fabric properties. Modification of properties of natural protein fibers through graft copolymerization has become an attractive means of chemical modification of these fibers, since such treatments; in general, improve some of the disadvantages associated with these fibers. Some vital changes in properties like photo yellowing, wash and wear, wrinkle recovery, water repellency, improved dye ability, soil resistance and thermal stability can be brought about by grafting with various vinyl monomers 3, 7, 10. Much work has been carried out during past years on grafting of mulberry and tussah silk fibroins with vinyl monomers using different initiators. 12,13,

Experimental Methods

Materials

Sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) and Ammonium Ceric Sulphate Dihydrate extrapure AR ($(\text{NH}_4)_4\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were purchased from Sisco Research Laboratories Pvt.Ltd.Plant site 2: H-4, MIDC, Taloja - 410208, Maharashtra, India. Zinc chloride (ZnCl_2) extra pure was purchased from Lobachemic Pvt. Ltd,107, WodehouseRoad, Jehangir Villa,Mumbai-400005,India. Acrylonitrile monomer was purchased from S.d Fine – Chem Limited Mumbai 400030. Oxalic Acid ($(\text{COOH})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was purchased from MediLise Chemicals, Kannur - 670009,Kerala, India. N,N Dimethyl formamide (DMF) ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{NO}$) and Hydrochloric acid (HCl) were purchased from Rankem, RFCL Limited A-3,Okhla Industrial Area, Phase -1, New Delhi- 110020. Double distilled water was used throughout the experiment.

Experimental Methods

Degumming

Degumming is the process of removing the sericin, or silk gum, from silk. Removing the gum improves the sheen, color, hand, and texture of the silk. Because the gum can serve as a protective layer, it is typically left on the silk until it is ready to dye. In some cases, the fabric is woven to completion and then degummed, to protect the yarn from abrasion on the loom.

Degumming by Heating

The silk fibroin was weighed and kept in an oven at 30°C for 24 hours. The weight is noted and percentage of degumming was calculated.

$$\text{Percentage degumming} = \frac{\text{Initial weight of silk fibroin} - \text{Final weight of silk fibroin}}{\text{Initial weight of silk fibroin}} \times 100$$

Degumming using Sodium Carbonate

0.2 Molar sodium carbonate was prepared and previously weighed silk fibroin was added to the Na₂CO₃ solution and heated for 1 hour at 70°C. After the removal of whole sericin, the fibroin was filtered off and washed with distilled water. Then it dried in an oven at 30°C for 24 hours. Weight was noted, and the percentage of degumming was calculated.

$$\text{Percentage degumming} = \frac{\text{Initial weight of silk fibroin} - \text{Final weight of silk fibroin}}{\text{Initial weight of silk fibroin}} \times 100$$

Preparation of Silk Solution

80% of ZnCl₂ (100ml) was prepared. The degummed silk fibroin (20mg) was dissolved in ZnCl₂ aqueous solution at 70°C under constant stirring for several hours.

Grafting

The graft co-polymerization reaction was conducted in 100ml reaction flask containing solutions of silk fibroin (20ml) and required amount of acrylonitrile, 0.1M oxalic acid (5ml), double distilled water, 0.1M HCl (2ml) of different concentration was immersed in a thermo stated water bath. Under gentle mixing, an appropriate amount of 0.1M ceric ammonium sulphate was added. The reaction was carried out at 30°C. After the desired reaction time the polymer was filtered off. The residue was treated with DMF. The undissolved residue was removed. Then the product was dried at 50°C. Weight was noted.

Result and Discussion

Percentage of Degumming

Degumming by Heating

The initial weight of silk fibroin = 0.3670g
 The final weight of silk fibroin = 0.3324g
 = 9.4277% at 30°C / 24 hours

$$\text{Percentage degumming} = \frac{\text{Initial weight of silk fibroin} - \text{Final weight of silk fibroin}}{\text{Initial weight of silk fibroin}} \times 100$$

Degumming by Sodium Carbonate

The initial weight of silk fibroin = 0.3670g
 The final weight of silk fibroin = 0.2915g
 = 20.5722% at 30°C / 24 hours

$$\text{Percentage degumming} = \frac{\text{Initial weight of silk fibroin} - \text{Final weight of silk fibroin}}{\text{Initial weight of silk fibroin}} \times 100$$

Effect of Monomer concentration on grafting of polymerization

The graft copolymerization of acrylonitrile on to silk fibroin was investigated by varying the monomer concentration (0.0075 - 0.22785 mol /dm³). The effect of monomer concentration on grafting polymerization rate (R_g) was studied in the region of (0.0075 – 0.2287 mol/dm³). The

initial rate and percentage conversion were found to be increase with the increase in monomer concentration, when the concentration of monomer is increased. The availability of monomer molecules in the propagation step increases which obviously increase the rate of grafting polymerization. The exponent with respect to monomer concentration was found to be 1.0. The order of the reaction with respect to monomer concentration is calculated from the plot of R_g versus $\log [M]$. The order with respect to monomer concentration was found to be unity in the above said range. At highest concentration of monomer, the rate decreases because of increases in viscosity of the medium, due to the solubility of the polymer in the monomer rendering the diffusion of the ions higher than unity is indicative of the occurrence of cage effect.¹⁵

Effect of Initiator [Ce(IV)] on the rate of grafting polymerization

The initial rate, as well as the maximum conversion increases with increase in the Ce(IV) concentration in the range of ($2.5 - 7.5 \times 10^{-3}$ mol/dm³). This is due to the fact that increase in Ce (IV) concentration increases the rate of production of primary radicals, which intern increases the grafting polymerization rate and maximum conversion. The order with respect to [Ce(IV)] was found to be fractional from a plot of $\log R_g$ versus $\log [ce(IV)]$, which clearly indicate that termination occurs through bimolecular interaction of growing polymer chain radicals.^{15,16} The Molecular weight decreases with increase of ce(IV) concentration, which can be explained by the fact that increasing concentration of Ce(IV) provides more chance for premature termination of growing chain radicals, which intern reduces the degree of polymerization.^{15,16}

Effect of temperature on rate of grafting polymerization

The grafting polymerization reaction has been studied at different temperatures from 30 to 40°C.

The initial rate of graft polymerization was found to be increases steadily with increase of temperature. Thereafter decreases above 60° C. It may be due to an increase in the system, leading to their efficient termination.

The activation energy (E_a) = 33.690 kJ/mole was calculated from Arrhenius plots of $\log R_g$ versus $1/T$ in the temperature range of 30 – 40° C. The other thermodynamic parameters were calculated from the Eyring plots are:

Energy of activation (E_a) = 33.690 k J/mole

$H^\ddagger = 31.127$ kJ/mole; $S^\ddagger = -209.89$ J/K/ mole ; and $G^\ddagger = 64.0$ kJ /mole ,

The reaction, which was initially homogeneous but as soon as the grafting polymerization started, due to the formation of an insoluble product become heterogeneous. Controlling the experiment involving in the individual addition of cerium (IV) or oxalic acid to the monomer solution did not induce grafting polymerization. Suggesting that the free radicals formed in situ by the cerium (IV) – oxalic acid system was responsible for graft polymerization . Based on the above results the following mechanistic scheme is proposed.

Mechanism and rate law

It has been assumed that cerium (IV), species present in sulfuric acid are $ce^{4+}(aq)$, $ce(OH)_3^+(aq)$ and $CeSO_4^+$. Since the effect of HSO_4^- ion on the reaction under investigation is negligible role of $CeSO_4^+$ is ruled out. Therefore, a combined role of $Ce^{4+}(aq)$ and $Ce(OH)_3^+(aq)$ can be envisaged, as observed in many Ce (IV) reactions. In fact $Ce(OH)_3^+(aq)$ should be considered as more reactive in view of the decrease in rate with increase in $[H^+]$.

Oxalic acid exists in the form of a cation, $HOOC-COOH$ in the strongly acidic medium. The most likely reaction mechanism that can satisfactorily explain the observed data shown in Scheme 1.

$$-d[\text{Ce}^{4+}]/dt = k_2 [\text{complex}]$$

Initiation

Propagation

Termination

Steady state principle is not included

Since the propagation is the stage that involves the major consumption of the monomer, the role of monomer loss can be expressed in terms of propagation only :

$$R_p = -d[\text{M}]/dt = k_p [\text{RM}\cdot 1] [\text{M}]$$

Based on the usual assumption that the radical reactivity is independent of the radical chain length, the rate of graft polymerization becomes,

$$R_g = k_p [\text{RM}\cdot_x] [\text{M}]$$

In the overall graft polymerization, the rate of initiation and the rate of termination become equal.

Thus the dependence of R_p on $[\text{M}]^{1/2}$, $[\text{Ce(IV)}]^{1/2}$, $[\text{OA}]^{1/2}$, all of which are observed, are consistent with the experimental results. The low energy of activation is an indication of the high reactivity and provides direct experimental evidence of the existence of transient radical intermediates generated in redox reactions. It also enables the identification of these radicals as end groups of the polymer. Further work on the kinetics of polymerization and graft copolymerization of various vinyl monomers initiated by the reaction of Cerium (IV) and other transition metal ions with suitable reductants are in our laboratories.

Product analysis

To characterize the molecular structure of acrylonitrile grafted silk, the FTIR spectra was used. Acrylonitrile grafted silk fibroin shows the absorption band of the two pure components, whose intensities are roughly related to the weight ratio of PAN and silk fibroin in the graft copolymer. Grafted silk shows absorption band of fibroin at 1654cm^{-1} (Amide - I), 1514cm^{-1} (Amide - II), 1226cm^{-1} (Amide - III), 697cm^{-1} (Amide - IV) which assigned to silk form. Besides these absorption bands, there is an absorption band at 3388cm^{-1} which corresponds to OH group. While some peaks due to grafted monomer could be evidenced in addition. The spectra of acrylonitrile grafted silk show additional band 2244cm^{-1} (C N stretching) and 1455cm^{-1} (C- H bending), 2928cm^{-1} (C-H stretching).

Mechanism of Graft Copolymerization

A graft copolymer is a system comprised of a backbone material (silk in this case) to which a second polymer is attached (Poly (acrylonitrile) at the reactive site along the macromolecular chain. Grafting of vinyl monomer to silk molecule is a typical free radical polymerization reaction, which involves three distinct aspects, such as initiation, propagation, and termination. The formation of free radical on the silk molecule can occur by the hemolytic cleavage processes,

such as dehydrogenation, dehydroxylation, and depolymerization. The location of the free radical sites on the silk molecule and within the fibrous structure is dependent on the method of initiation of such sites, on the physical and chemical properties of silk molecule and the pH of the reaction mixture.

Aim and Scope

The main aim of this work is Help promote THE INTERNATIONAL YEAR OF NATURAL FIBERS 2009. The international year will raise awareness of their importance not only to producers and industry, but to consumers and the environment. Most synthetic fibers cannot match the “breathability” of natural fiber textiles, which creates natural ventilation (Healthy choice). By choosing natural fibers, we can contribute to the economies of developing countries and help fight hunger and rural poverty (responsible choice). Renewable and carbon neutral, natural fibers leave residues that can be used to generate electricity, and they are 100% biodegradable.

Noting also that the diverse range of natural fibers produced in many countries provides an important source of income for farmers, and thus can play an important role in contributing to food security and in eradicating poverty and hence on contributing to the achievement of the Millennium development goals;

1. Decides to declare 2009 the international year of natural fibers.
2. Invite the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations to facilitate the observance of the year, in collaboration with governments, regional and international organizations, non-government organizations, the private sector and relevant organizations of the United Nations system, and also invites the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations to keep the general assembly informed of progress made in this regard.
3. Calls upon governments and relevant regional and international organizations to make voluntary contributions and to tender other forms of support to the year;
4. Invites non-governmental organizations and the private sector to make voluntary contributions and to tender other forms of support to support the year;
5. Encourage all the governments, the United Nations system and all other actors to take advantage of the year in order to increase awareness of the importance of these natural products.

Objective

Natural fibers are even though wide range of advantageous than synthetic fibers mentioned above but they are poor mechanical properties, susceptible towards fungus, mites and insects. So to overcome these limitations structural modification of natural fibers such as co-polymer, block co-polymers, blending, composites and grafting are required. So we choose grafting of natural fibers with monomers, polymers etc, it enhances the mechanical properties, hydrophobicity, chemical resistance, microbial resistance like fungus, mites, worms, insects and flame resistance. Then these modified materials used for constructing materials in house, vehicles, aerospace vehicles, biocomposites, furnishings, furnitures, wood modifications.

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Table 1 Effect of Monomer on the Rate of Grafting Polymerization

[Ce(IV)]x103 Mol/dm ³	[OA] x103 Mol/dm ³	[HCl] x102 Mol/dm ³	[AN] x Mol/dm ³	Temperature K	Rate of Grafting R _g x104mol/s
5.0	5.0	2.0	0.0075	308	1.0263
5.0	5.0	2.0	0.0152	308	2.0785
5.0	5.0	2.0	0.0228	308	3.1170
5.0	5.0	2.0	0.0304	308	4.1562
5.0	5.0	2.0	0.0380	308	5.1951
5.0	5.0	2.0	0.0456	308	6.2344
5.0	5.0	2.0	0.0608	308	8.3138
5.0	5.0	2.0	0.0912	308	12.4709
5.0	5.0	2.0	0.122	308	16.6264
5.0	5.0	2.0	0.1520	308	20.7826
5.0	5.0	2.0	0.2287	308	17.5634
5.0	5.0	2.0	-----	308	-----

Table 2 Effect of Initiator Concentration onto the Rate of Grafting Polymerization

[AN] mol/dm ³	[Ce (IV)]x103 Mol/dm ³	[OA] x 103 Mol/dm ³	[HCl] x 102 Mol/dm ³	Temperature K	R _g x104 Mol/s
0.0608	2.5	5.0	2.0	308	10.33
0.0608	3.2	5.0	2.0	308	11.81
0.0608	5.0	5.0	2.0	308	16.0
0.0608	7.5	5.0	2.0	308	13.95
0.0608	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----

Fig 1 The Effect of Manomer on Grafting Rate

Fig 2 Arrhenius plt

Fig 3 FTIR Spectra of Acrylonitrile Grafted Silk

Scheme 1

